

The Effect of Misinterpretation of Scriptures in Pentecostal Churches in Ugandan: A Case of Full Gospel Church Kirombe-Luzira Kampala

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DECLARATION

I Naloka Baker do hereby declare that THE EFFECT OF MISINTERPRETA-TION OF SCRIPTURES IN PENTECOSTAL CHURCHES IN UGANDAN: A CASE OF FULL GOSPEL CHURCH KIROMBE-LUZIRA KAMPALA mirrors my original work and has not been presented to any academic institution whatsoever.

Signature..... Date.....12—5-2023.

LETTER OF AUTHORISATION

I NALOKA BAKER FREDERICK do here by attest that this academic book represents a true picture of findings to the best of my understanding.

Signature.....Date...12-5-2023.

SUPERVISORS RECOMMENDATION

This is to attest that NALOKA BAKER FREDERICK completed his academic research book with our approval.

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2. Signature.....

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Principal Research Supervisor

Date.....25-05-2023.

DEDICATION

I dedicate this research to God, my late parents, my dear wife and children, Sam Sekaku for their assistance.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

My gratitude goes to my group members as well as our research supervisor Professor Kibalama Johnson and his assistant; Dr. Kitaka who introduced to me this program and encouraged me to take it on with all the responsibilities that I hold. I never knew I could handle it, however the encouragement and time invested to show me that it is possible was and is all worth it.

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LISTS OF ACRONYMS

WOF : Word of Faith
P5 : Prosperity, Praise, Power, Prayer and Permanent Miracles.
77 DOGS : Seventy Seven Days of Glory.
IV : Independent Variable
DV : Dependent variable.
MV : Mediating variable
USA : United States of America
TIS : Theological Interpretation of Scripture.
PAG-USA : Pentecostal Assemblies of God (USA).
PAG-CANADA: Pentecostal Assemblies of God (Canada).

ABSTRACT

This research is about identifying the effects of misinterpreting scriptures and identify principles that help proper interpreting the Bible. These principles are called hermeneutics.

Scripture interpretation is so critical that Apostle Peter emphasized it by warning the unlearned and unstable people who were misinterpreting Paul's letters as they did other scriptures to their destruction (*2Pe:3:15*).

Scripture handling is so efficacious that misinterpretation may cause grave errors.

Proper hermeneutics will help bring out the authors intended meaning which will be exegetically explained to the congregation.

Sound Bible interpretation will safeguard from imposing the reader's meaning (eisegesis).

A number of reasons why people differ in opinion from one another is that they use different measuring rods of interpretation.

CHAPTER ONE INTRODUCTION

This study examined the effects of misinterpretation of scriptures in Pentecostal Churches in Uganda: A Case of Full Gospel Church Kirombe-Kampala. This chapter contains the Title; the problems background; purpose of the study; objectives; study scope; hypothesis; significance and definition of terms. Full Gospel Churches of Uganda are over 1600 churches country-wide with its mother church headquarters at Makerere Hill Road plot number 55-59, is situated.

A full grasp of scriptures is attained when exegesis of Biblical text is in tandem with the theological interpretation of scripture. This study geared at over coming the disparity between exegeses and theological interpretation.

A. *Title of Proposed Study:*

The Effect of Misinterpretation of Scriptures in Pentecostal Churches in Ugandan: A CASE OF FULL GOSPEL CHURCH KIROMBE-LUZIRA KAMPALA.

B. *Background to the Study.*

Misinterpretation of scriptures existed even during the time of Biblical Apostles. Apostle Peter warns about those who misinterpreted scriptures to their own destruction (2Peter 3:15-16).

Mass misinterpretation of scriptures started with the contemporary theological movements after World War 1. As a result, the way we view God and ourselves has changed from orthodox views to outright heresy. Even the way we pray and petition God has degenerated to the arrogant declaring and decreeing and even commanding God.

Hermeneutics as a subject is linked to ancient Greeks in their literature and Bible exegesis of Jewish Christian traditions.

C. *The Conceptual Background:*

Poor interpretation of scriptures causes the following which this paper tried to correct.

- It causes a distorted understanding of the almighty God, in that people may reduce God to a man status and promote man to a God status.
- It may cause our prayers to be distorted as well. Instead of praying and petitioning God, we may end up commanding Him to do what we want.
- Misinterpreting scripture may also see or view ourselves with high self-esteem instead of seeing ourselves with total depravity.
- This may also cause us err into a theological impasse by ascertaining the meaning out of context. 1.3: Statement of the problem.

D. *Statement of the Problem*

Proliferation of false doctrine and false teachers due to misinterpretation and misapplication of scriptures.

The gaps in the existing literature are, that the other researchers have not addressed is the resultant effects on gender leadership role distinctions. They have not come boldly to write apologetic books to address the gap. It against this background that this study is being carried out.

E. *The Goal of the Study.*

The goal was to clearly identify and document principles used in proper interpretation of scriptures and weed out doctrinal errors.

➤ *The Objective of the Research.*

- To sport interpretation and application errors and provide solutions for that problem.
- To assess the damage the wealth and health gospel has affected the faith of contemporary Christianity.
- To create an emphasis of identifying wolves in sheep's clothing and their false teaching and recommending instituting oversight and accountability management system to maintain doctrinal purity.
- What extent does extra-biblical revelation knowledge affect scripture-based theology?

➤ *Research Questions.*

- What is the effect of interpretation errors on identification of false doctrine in Uganda?
- What is the effect of interpretation errors helping the spread of WOF Theology in Uganda?
- Is there an oversight and accountability mechanism to enforce and maintain doctrinal purity of the church?
- Does reliance on extra-biblical revelations significantly affect doctrinal purity in Uganda?

F. *Alternative Hypothesis.*

There is a significant effect of misinterpretation and misapplication of scriptures.

- *HA1:* The misinterpretation and misapplication of scriptures do significantly affect identifying false doctrine.
- *HA2:* The misinterpretation and misapplication of scriptures do significantly cause the spread of the wealth and health false gospel of contemporary Christianity in Uganda.
- *HA3:* Oversight and accountability mechanism (Denominational Regulation) do significantly affect the doctrinal purity, unity and conduct of the Pentecostal churches in Uganda.
- *HA4:* Extra-Biblical revelations do significantly affect the doctrinal purity in Pentecostal churches in Uganda.

G. *Proposed Research Design, Methods and Procedures*

The study used related literature review for secondary and primary data sources. Encyclopedias, commentaries, theological dictionaries, concordances, and other theological reference tools. The original King James Bible, Luganda Bible, Good News Bible, Standard Amplified Bible. Various Christian books authored by Pentecostal charismatics. While primary data was using self-administered questionnaires and structured interview guides. The study looked at a population of 80 pastors and ministers; a sample size of 100 was derived using Krejcie and Morgan 1970.

H. *Contribution to Knowledge.*

This study will provide a big knowledge in the body of Christ which will enable church leaders and other Christians, to weed out unbiblical theological speculations. It will provide critical thinking instincts which the noble Bereans used to examine the truth of Paul's teachings using the plumbline of scripture (Acts 17:10-12).

I. *Scope of the Study.*

➤ *Geographical Scope.*

This study was carried out in a Pentecostal church in Uganda, for the purpose of this study; the researcher undertook this study in Full Gospel Church-Kirombe Luzira in Kampala, and branches countrywide. No single study has been conducted to this ministry to assess the effect of misinterpretation of scriptures, thus filling the gaps of the study.

➤ *Theoretical Scope*

The research examined a number of theories namely; the literal, moral, allegories, anagoges and other scholarly principles of interpretations. This study examined the extent to which these theories have been violated in Biblical studies. These are discussed here below.

➤ *Content Scope.*

The research investigated the Interpretation of scriptures, extra-biblical revelations, Oversight and Accountability to scriptures: as independent variables; using four measures namely; false doctrine, identification of wolves in sheep's clothing, proliferation of WOF (Prosperity) Theology, a rapid rise of false prophets and absence of), lack of doctrinal unity and oneness (Quality assurance: as dependent variables.

➤ *Time Scope*

The research concentrated on the period 2010-2021 because it is the period when there have been much claimed revivals in Uganda like P5 and 77DOGS. In this period Kayanja (Vol-2017), wrote that the Church is weak, confused and accepts all sorts of messages which are different from what the Apostles wrote.

Furthermore, Evangelist Semugoma (2022), reiterated that 2022 was a year of revival in Uganda as per Benny Hinn's 2019 prophesy in a declaration during a gathering dubbed 'Experience Conference' at the Maker's House Chapel International in Accra Ghana 2019.

➤ *Units of Analysis*

Unit of Analysis was Kirombe Full Gospel Church and Unit of Inquiry were church ministers and members because they were considered to have information necessary for the study Subject.

CHAPTER TWO LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Introduction

This chapter includes theoretical review, conceptual review, empirical literature review from the findings of previous researches related to the study variables and objectives. Research gaps are also indicated.

B. Historical Background.

According to Vern Poythress (1999). There are three general concepts to understand about any passage of Scripture. First, the original time and context, which includes the personal perspective of the writer, the normative perspective of the text itself, and the situational perspective of the original audience. Second, it is necessary to understand the transmission of Scripture includes contemplating the message being sent through the text, taking into account the concerns of individual writers/translators as well as its broader role in the unraveling narrative of history. Finally, Poythress instructs interpreters to understand Scripture as "what God is saying now" to the individual as well as to the modern church.

Henry A. Virkler (1981), argues that there are several types of analysis needed to identify what the author intended to communicate in the biblical passage:

- Lexical-syntactical analysis: This step looks at the words used and the way the words are used. Different order of the sentence, the punctuation, the tense of the verse are all aspects that are looked at in the lexical syntactical method. Here, lexicons and grammar aids can help in extracting meaning from the text.
- Historical/cultural analysis: The history and culture surrounding the authors is important to understand to aid in interpretation. For instance, understanding the Jewish sects of the Palestine and the government that ruled Palestine in New Testament times increases understanding of Scripture. And, understanding the connotations of positions such as the High Priest and that of the tax collector helps us know what others thought of the people holding these positions.
- Contextual analysis: A verse out of context can often be taken to mean something completely different from the intention. This method focuses on the importance of looking at the context of a verse in its chapter, book and even biblical context.
- Theological analysis: It is often said that a single verse usually doesn't make a theology. This is because Scripture often touches on issues in several books. For instance, gifts of the Spirit are spoken about in Romans, Ephesians and 1 Corinthians. To take a verse from Corinthians without taking into account other passages that deal with the same topic can cause a poor interpretation.
- Special literary analysis: There are several special literary aspects to look at, but the overarching theme is that each genre of Scripture has a different set of rules that applies to it. Of the genres found in Scripture, there are: narratives, histories, prophecies, apocalyptic writings, poetry, psalms and letters. In these, there are differing levels of allegory, figurative language, metaphors, similes and literal language. For instance, the apocalyptic writings and poetry have more figurative and allegorical language than does the narrative or historical writing. These must be addressed, and the genre recognized to gain a full understanding of the intended meaning.

However, Poythress (1999), argues that the study of the Bible must acknowledge three dimensions: God as the speaker, the Bible as His speech, and the people to whom He speaks. But to do this, biblical hermeneutics needs to unravel the layers of meaning found within the "speaker, discourse, and hearer." For some, such as Howard Hendricks and Chuck Swindoll (2007), this can be as simple as taking three steps: observing the text, interpreting the text, and applying the text to one's life.

Another important principle is the Biblical hermeneutics that scripture always best interpreter of scripture. We therefore compare scripture with scripture in order to determine the meaning of the passage

➤ *Theoretical Review*

The researcher identified four theories for this study, the literal, moral, allegorical, anagogical, and others, according to the Editors of Encyclopedia Britannica, 2022.

➤ *Theoretical Underpinnings of the Study*

The researcher identified **at least** four theories for this study, the literal, moral, allegorical, anagogical, and others, according to the Editors of Encyclopedia Britannica, 2022.

➤ *Literal Theory*

This one state that a Bible text should be interpreted according to plain meaning conveyed by its grammatical construction and historical context. The literal meaning coincides with the authors intention.

➤ *Moral Interpretation Theory*

This one seeks to establish exegetical principles by which ethical lessons may be drawn from various parts of the Bible.

➤ *Allegorical Theory.*

This interpretation conveys a meaning beyond those things mentioned in the text. Eg Jesus said that “Am the door or a vine tree”. It does not mean Jesus in a tree or actual physical door.

➤ *Anagogical Theory*

This theory deals with interpreting the mystical aspects as they relate to the life to come.

➤ *Compare Scripture with Scripture*

Comparing scripture with another scripture will help Bible readers to determine the meaning of a passage. This will safeguard getting contradictory meanings from Bible text.

➤ *Author’s Intention of Meaning.*

Bible readers should assume the author’s context, historically, and literal forms of conventions the author was working in.

C. Conceptual Review

This section shows the researcher’s discussion about the definitions and meanings of the main study variables (misinterpretation of scriptures, misapplication, extra-biblical revelations and proliferation and overall performance of the church. and their measurements based on views from various scholars. This study encompassed the assessment of misinterpretation of scriptures and church performance as well as testing the mediating effect of denominational oversight as to how the two variables relate. In consonant with the model (Fig. 2.3), the researcher in his own conceptualization, attributed the performance of a church like Full Gospel Church to the effectiveness of rightly handling the Word of God by proper interpretation principles but also the extent to which there is effective oversight supervision by denomination heads, doctrinal accountability by the church leaders. As indicated in the model, proper interpretations are expected to result into weeding out false doctrine and wolves in sheep’s clothing. It was also assumed that for proper interpretation to have a stronger effect on performance, there should be strong oversight supervision by denomination heads who cause church leaders to account for their doctrine and church practice.

Independent Variables

Dependent Variables

Fig 1 Conceptual Framework Relating Misinterpretations and Emergence of False Doctrine and False Teachers
Source: Adopted and modified from Dr. Olwol 2022.

The Figure 1 above shows the negative linkage between misinterpreting, misapplying, and the overall performance of the church and the mediating effect of overseers’ roles and accountability to scripture.

D. Conceptual Framework Description.

As per the framework in Fig. 2.3, indicates that misinterpretation of scriptures and entertainment of extra-biblical revelations (independent variables) can affect doctrinal purity and performance of Churches independently.

The conceptual framework suggests that the more scriptures are misinterpreted, the more churches degenerate into false doctrine, (arrow H₁). Likewise, strong exegesis of scriptures will enhance the spiritual health of churches. It is indicated in Fig. 2.3 that misinterpretation of scriptures can affect church performance directly or through a mediator variable, which is oversight (Denominational overseers’ roles).

According to this framework, the researcher assumed that there is a correlation between the independent variables (Misinterpretation and extra-biblical Revelations) and the mediator variable (Oversight supervision by overseers), as indicated by arrow H₂. Misinterpretation mechanisms were conceived by the researcher to be significantly related with oversight and accountability to scripture. Oversight roles means that all church leaders concerned are held responsible for their erroneous teachings and practices. In this case, individual biblical teachers are aware that there are checks and balances by the moderating variable of oversight. So their compliance to proper exegesis of scripture is expected to be high. At the same time, oversight function is affected by the dependent variable, because if the overseers do their oversight agency well, false doctrine will be at bay (arrow H₃). The researcher assumed that when churches interpreted scriptures properly, spiritual health will improve and vice versa.

Finally, the researcher also hypothesized that oversight roles mediate the relationship between misinterpretation and sound doctrine in Full Gospel Church. Under the principles of mediation (Hayes, 2012), as indicated by arrow H₂, the independent variable (predictor) is expected to have a significant correlation with the mediator and also the mediator is expected to have a significant correlation with the dependent variable (as indicated by H₃). For the mediation assumption to be fulfilled, the coefficient of the predictor reduces when the mediator variable is introduced in the model at the same time with the predictor.

The researcher assumed that when there is effective Bible interpretations and strong oversight supervision, the performance of the church will be better than when the correlation of each is taken alone. The overall performance of Full Gospel Church was measured by reviewing how the Bible is interpreted through Bible principles aiming at testing the application, spread of the prosperity gospel and presence of doctrinal unity and oneness.

CHAPTER THREE METHODOLOGY

A. Introduction.

In this chapter, contains the platform on which data collection and processing were carried out. It presents the methodology, the research design, study population, sample size, sampling strategies, data collection methods, and instruments, data collection procedures, data analysis etc.

B. Research Philosophy

In tandem with Saunder (2009), philosophy of research is the way the researcher forms an understanding of the natural world. It is therefore the way the researcher's knowledge of the world is constructed. This philosophical orientation defines their interpretations of different aspects and forms an important part in the kind of knowledge that exists in the various fields of study. In this regard, therefore, the philosophical beliefs that pre-occupy the researcher dictate the way they collect data about a particular phenomenon, and how they analyze and interpret those data. There are various contrasting philosophical orientations or schools of thought researchers can follow or in which the beliefs of any current researcher can fall.

- Explain the methodological approach.
- Describe the data collection methods used.
- Describe data analysis methods used,
- Justify Your Methodology

This study followed positivist interpretative and pragmatism philosophies. In line with these philosophies, a quantitative research paradigm was employed. With the quantitative paradigm, the researcher investigated the variables studied (indicates that misinterpretation of scriptures and entertainment of extra-biblical revelations (independent variables) can affect doctrinal purity and performance of Churches independently.) by surveying the perceptions of respondents, which were then quantified and described with a simple percentage description. The reason for the choice of this paradigm design is because it's deductive, with variables and hypotheses clearly defined in advance of data collection. This method needed use of logical, deductive thinking. Questionnaires with limited options was used not only to ease the respondent's response but due to the limited time and limited finance was considered. Since the researchers aim and objective looked to measuring or testing something, hence the use of qualitative data collection methods.

Research in the social science fields calls for particular epistemological reflections based on theoretical developments and empirical practice (Vasilachis de Gialdino, Irene, 2011). The epistemological philosophy examines the nature of knowledge. The rationality of beliefs and justification, nased on four arears : 1) analysis of the nature of knowledge and how it relates to ideas like truth, belief and justification (Steup & Zalta, 2014): (2), various problems of skepticism: (3), the sorce of scope of knowledge and justified beliefs: and (4) the criteria for knowledge and justification. Therefore, epistemological studies aim at finding the meaning of knowledge, before taking a conclusion. According to Vasilachis de Gialdino (2011)" epistemologists always reflect on the answers to research questions in various ways, so some answers to research questions may apply in one field but may not apply in another. That is why epistemological reflections are needed, to allow researchers to expound on the different answers to the questions asked. This means interpretations of answers need to be critical to ensure that what the respondent wanted to mean is what the researcher interprets not what the researcher wants or understands. What is revealed can be known in separate ways so that certain occurrences may arise from two or more situations, explaining their occurrence. So what is known and how it is known are quite different things and so researchers need to be careful on how they conduct their investigations. This means that how a certain investigation is done determines the conclusion arrived at. To arrive at meaningful conclusions, the researcher employed only data collection in questionnaires form.

The positivist philosophy is derived from the beliefs of the famous French scholar Augustine Comte who maintained that observation and reason are the major means of understanding human behavior (Cohen,2000). It is further derived that knowledge is based on experience of the senses which can be obtained through these assumptions; which means events are caused by other circumstances, and understanding such links are necessary for prediction and control.

C. Research Design

This study followed an integrated different component of the study in a coherent and logical way, and ensured effective address of the research problem.

D. Target Population

This study's targeted a population of 800 members of the Church.

E. Sample Size.

The study was based on a sample size of 80 members drawn from a population of 100 members.

F. Sampling Method.

It was random selection.

G. Data Collection Instruments.

This study was based mainly on both primary and secondary data; primary data was collected using one instrument, the questionnaires. The questionnaires used to collect data for this study were researched developed. The questionnaires were used because the respondents were educated enough to read and interpret and answer questions correctly. All the questions in this questionnaire were close-ended. This was preferred because of the vast experience of the respondents and it was assumed that each one of them would give a definite response since they are the corporations' policy implementers; uncertain responses were assumed not to be directly answering the questions of the study.

H. Data Collection Procedures.

The following steps were taken during the data gathering process of this study;

➤ *Before the Administration of Questionnaires.*

The researcher acquired an introductory letter from the directorate of research of the East African Polytechnic College-Kyambogo Kampala, which helped to introduce the researcher to the respective church -Full Gospel Kiroombe Luzira. Upon this, the researcher was given permission to collect data for the research. Then 80 copies of questionnaires were produced and distributed to the respondents, by the researcher with the help of three research assistants, by the researcher who were well oriented prior to this exercise, about the methods and techniques of data collection and administration of the questionnaire.

➤ *During Questionnaire Administration*

During the data collection phase, the researcher and the three assistants guided the respondents on how to fill in the questionnaires. The researcher and the three research assistants guided the respondents on how to fill in the questionnaires and requested them to do so correctly and objectively. Respondents were requested to read through before completing the questionnaire.

➤ *After Questionnaire Administration*

On the retrieval of the answered questionnaires, the researcher checked each to ensure that each questionnaire was fully completed as required. Thereafter, the data was before it could be analyzed.

I. Data Analysis.

The collected data were processed data before it was finally analyzed.

J. Ethical Considerations

To ensure that ethical principles in research are complied with, the researcher carried out the following;

➤ *Permission to Conduct Research:*

an introduction letter was given in writing from by the East African Polytechnic College.

Respondents' freedom: Respondents were free to give information or to not to give. They were educated about the purpose of the study. They were guided to read through before signing an acceptance form.

➤ *Respondents' Anonymity:*

Maximum confidentiality of participants' was ensured and their responses was observed and never disclosed.

➤ *Avoiding Plagiarism:*

The researcher made sure that academic works and information from other people were properly recognised by citing and referencing them. In case scholars' works were directly transplanted, they were put in quotation marks and authors were properly cited.

CHAPTER FOUR

DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

A. Introduction

Chapter four of the dissertation is an empirical section of the research, in which the researcher presented the empirical findings of the study and shows how those findings were arrived at. In this chapter the recap of our research focus was The Effect of Misinterpretation of Scriptures in Pentecostal Churches in Ugandan: A CASE OF FULL GOSPEL CHURCH KIROMBE-LUZIRA KAMPALA. And the null hypothesis was to test whether there was a significant effect of misinterpretation and misapplication of scriptures with the objectives of identify misinterpretation and application errors and to provide proper interpretations and applications; to assess the damage the wealth and health gospel has affected the faith of contemporary Christianity; to create an emphasis of identifying wolves in sheep's clothing and their false teaching by putting in place an oversight and accountability mechanism to towards doctrinal purity and the extent extra-biblical revelation knowledge affect scripture-based theology.

In this empirical chapter, there are several subsections, starting with the response rate, profile characteristics of respondents, description of data collected on the dependent variable and finally presentation of findings as per the study objectives.

B. Response Rate

According to Amin (2005), analysis of the rate at which respondents responded to the data collection instrument is important to ensure that the data collected can be relied upon. In line with this study, of all the 66 questionnaires administered, 51 were returned fully filled, suggesting 77.27% response rate. Table 4.1 presents these results.

Table 1 Response Rate

Questionnaires	Frequency	Percentage
Questionnaires distributed according to sample size	66	100
Returned Questionnaires	60	90.90
Fully filled and usable Questionnaires	51	77.27
Response Rate	51	77.27
Response Rate as per sample size	51/51	100

Source: Field Data, 2023

As indicated in table 4.1, for the 66 questionnaires sent out in the field, a total of 60 were returned, but only 51 had been filled in a satisfactory way, yielding a 77.27% response rate. This response rate is above the minimum response rate of 75% according to Amin (2005).

C. Title of Proposed Objectives

The research findings noted that there was a significant practice of misinterpreting and misapplication of scriptures,

D. Study Problem and Objectives

The problem is the proliferation of false doctrine and false teachers due to misinterpretation and misapplication of scriptures.

The study aimed at clearly identifying and documenting principles which are used in proper interpretation of scriptures and weed out doctrinal errors. To identify misinterpretation and application errors and to provide proper interpretations and applications. To assess the damage the wealth and health gospel has affected the faith of contemporary Christianity. To create an emphasis of identifying wolves in sheep's clothing and their false teaching by putting in place an oversight and accountability system to towards doctrinal purity. To what extent does extra-biblical revelation knowledge affect scripture-based theology?

This study explored the questionnaire approach applied particularly on the presentation of findings from the responses. The self-administered questionnaires were used to collect data and were distributed to the respondents. The respondents included pastors, elders and other church members. The study used a simple analysis of percentages due to budget constraints.

E. Analysis of Findings

➤ *To identify misinterpretation and application errors and to provide proper interpretations and applications.*

The findings from the first objective revealed that 32 respondents out of 51 agreed and confirmed that scriptures (Luke 23:43, Eccl 12:7, Revelation 7:9-17) to imply that righteous people go direct to heaven immediately after death. This error amounts (63%) respondents.

➤ *To assess the damage the wealth and health gospel has affected the faith of contemporary Christianity.*

• *The findings from the second objective showed the following outcomes:*

Out of a population of respondents 31 out of 51 respondents misinterpreted 6 scriptures quoted to justify prosperity gospel (John 10:10, 2Corinthians 9:6, Prov 18:12, Psalms 89:34, Eph 1:3-4, 2Peter 1:2-13. This makes 70% rate of misinterpretation error.

➤ *To create an emphasis of identifying wolves in sheep's clothing and their false teaching by putting in place an oversight and accountability mechanism to towards doctrinal purity.*

On testing 1 Corinth 14:20 to find out whether logic is applicable in understanding scriptures, to which only 20 (39%) out of 51 respondents affirmed the use of Logic while 31ie.61% rejected the use of logic.

➤ *Isaiah 45:11-12 was tested to find out whether Christians are able to command God to give them what they want.* Only 7% agreed that Christians have the authority to command God to give them what they want, the rest disagreed.

➤ *On testing two scriptures Luke 23:43, Ecclesiastes 12:7,*

And Rev 7:9-17 to imply that they were real historical events that righteous people ascend directly to heaven before the resurrection.

It was found out that 32 respondents out of 51 (63%) agreed and confirmed that the righteous go to heaven.

➤ *As to whether the gifts of Apostles and Prophets were still in operation in churches today.*

Out of 15 respondents who answered this question, 12 agreed that gifts of apostles and prophets still exist, only 3 respondents disagreed. Making it 80% rate of agreement.

➤ *About whether Christians can be affected by generational curses.*

It was noted that 9 out of 16 respondents who answered this question, 56.25% confirmed generation curses can ravage Christians despite the sacrificial death of Christ on the cross.

➤ *To what extent does extra-biblical revelation knowledge affect scripture-based theology?*

On how God speaks in these last days, 32 out of 43 who answered this question affirmed that God still speaks through dreams, visions, angelic visitations, etc. as was in the Old Testament, making this 74.41% agreement in extra-biblical revelations outside scripture.

➤ *Analysis of the hypothesis of the study findings.*

The study used Alternative hypothesis. This is considered to be the opposite of the null hypothesis; an alternative hypothesis is denoted as H1 or Ha. It explicitly states that the dependent variable affects the independent variable.

There is a significant effect of misinterpretation and misapplication of scriptures.

- *HA1: The misinterpretation and misapplication of scriptures do significantly affect identifying false doctrine. As the findings revealed that 51% Christians misinterpreted the three scriptures (Luke 23:43, Eccl 12:7) to imply that righteous people go direct to heaven immediately after death, it may be difficult to identify false doctrine.*
- *HA2: The misinterpretation and misapplication of scriptures do significantly cause the spread of the wealth and health false gospel of contemporary Christianity in Uganda. This makes 70% rate of misinterpretation error so significant to confirm the hypothesis.*
- *HA3: Oversight and accountability mechanism (Denominational Regulation) do significantly affect the doctrinal purity, unity and conduct of the Pentecostal churches in Uganda. The findings of interpretation errors ranging from 7% to 80% as outlined in 4.3 above, confirms the alternative hypothesis of lack of overs to bring the church leadership to account for their errant doctrines.*
- *HA4: Extra-Biblical revelations do significantly affect the doctrinal purity in Pentecostal churches in Uganda. The findings that 32 out of 43 who answered this question affirmed that God still speaks through dreams, visions, angelic vis-itations, etc. as was in the Old Testament, making this 74.41% agreement in extra-biblical revelations outside scripture speaks volume about the rampant false doctrine and wolves in sheep's clothing.*

F. Conclusion.

The research focus of Ascertaining the *Effect of misinterpretation of scriptures in Pentecostal churches a Case of Full Gospel Church Kirombe* and the alternative Hypothesis of whether there was a significant effect of *misinterpretation and misapplying scriptures* has been attested by the empirical findings as detailed above. For example, the wealth and health gospel rampant in Pentecostal churches is noted due to misinterpret and misapply the premises God promised Israel as a nation and appropriate them to the church. It was concluded also that there lack of oversight supervision of overseers to ensure checks and balances of doctrinal unity and purity in line with the Full Gospel Statement of faith which the branch members expressed ignorance of by their skewed responses. For example, the first article of statement of faith says that *The Bible, inerrant and infallible and supreme and final authority in faith and life (2 Timothy 3:16; 2 Pet 1:20-21)* significant number of respondents believed in extra-biblical revelations side by side with the Bible. This is a wake-up call to church leaders to ensure doctrinal unity in all church branches by aligning their teachings with the mainstream statements of faith.

CHAPTER FIVE

DISCUSSIONS OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

A. Introduction.

In this chapter, the researcher presents a discussion of key study findings following the study objectives. The conclusions derived from the study findings are also presented as well as recommendations for church management and custodians of church policy. The chapter also shows the suggestions for further research.

B. Discussions of Findings.

Four specific objectives were investigated, which included The Effect of Misinterpretation of Scriptures in Pentecostal Churches in Ugandan: A CASE OF FULL GOSPEL CHURCH KIROMBE-LUZIRA KAMPALA;

- To identify misinterpretation and application errors and to provide proper interpretations and applications.
- To assess the damage the wealth and health gospel has affected the faith of contemporary Christianity.
- To create an emphasis of identifying wolves in sheep's clothing and their false teaching by putting in place an oversight and accountability mechanism to towards doctrinal purity.
- To what extent does extra-biblical revelation knowledge affect scripture-based theology?

In this discussion, the findings for each objective are first summarized and then discussed accordingly. To clearly identify and document principles which are used in proper interpretation of scriptures and weed out doctrinal errors.

➤ *To identify misinterpretation and application errors and to provide proper interpretations and applications.*

The misinterpretation of (Luke 23:43, Eccl 12:7) amounting to 65% rate is an indication that churches most likely misunderstand and misapply scriptures to their detriment. Jesus himself said He would be in the grave three days and nights after His crucifixion. Then how could He be with the thief in heaven or paradise at the same time?

In 1 Corinthians 15:3-4, Paul teaches that Jesus died, was buried and rose again according to scriptures. Paul did not mention going to paradise before the resurrection, but scriptures teach Jesus was dead for three days.

Then what did Jesus mean by "today". This misinterpretation comes due to a misplacement of a comma before the word "Today" by scholars who punctuated the Bible.

If a comma was placed after the word "Today", the proper meaning would have come out clearly meaning that Jesus assured the thief that day that the thief would be with Jesus one day but not the day they died. Another important point to prove that the thief did not go anywhere apart from the grave is found in 1 Corinthians 15:20-23, which states that Jesus was the first to come out of all people who have died., and when He comes back the second time, the rest of the dead will live again in the resurrection. So even the thief like the rest from Adam is still dead.

➤ *To assess the damage the wealth and health gospel has affected the faith of contemporary Christianity.*

The 70% rate of misinterpretation error means we pick verses out of context in which the author wrote them. In this way we are changing how we view God in His Word. When we pluck verses out of the story- e.g. Jeremiah 29:11, we miss out on the true meaning of the those verses. We get a partial truth from the out of context version. The true contextual meaning was a message sent to the Jewish community in exile whereby God was promising them a better future after decades of slavery.

➤ *To create an emphasis of identifying wolves in sheep's clothing and their false teaching by putting in place an oversight and accountability mechanism towards doctrinal purity.*

The findings of interpretation errors ranging from 7% to 80% as outlined in 4.3 above, covering a large spectrum of scriptures confirms the lack of overseers' supervisory role to force church leaders to account to scripture they claim in statements of faith. For example, use of logic was denied by a number of respondents to the tune of 61%.

Logic is the science of evaluating arguments and how we construct reason. Logic therefore, analyses how we construct reasonable arguments and draw fallacy-free conclusions. The introduction to the use of logic in apologetics will consider key issues such as the nature of God, the definition of faith, its importance to Christianity, religious epistemology, the nature of man and the human mind, and divine providence. Faith without logic is blind faith; and logic without faith is heresy.

Thomas B. Warren, 1920-2000, who was an American professor of philosophy of Religion and apologetics at the Harding school of Theology in Memphis, Tennessee, USA, defended the use of logic in hermeneutics by challenging the challenging both the irrational and the agnostic to rethink their position.

Any attempt to disparage or dismiss logic is self-refuting for the very reason that one must use logic in order to make their arguments against logic intelligible. As Gr. Johnson notes, "The opponents of logic must use the law of contradiction in order to denounce it. They must assume its legitimacy, in order to declare its illegitimate. They must assume its truth, in order to declare it false. They must present arguments if they wish to persuade us that argumentation is invalid. Wherever they turn, they are boxed in" Thus, any attack on logic is undermined by the antagonist's own use of it. Hence logic simply is unavoidable.

➤ *To what extent does extra-biblical revelation knowledge affect scripture-based theology?*

On how God speaks in the last days 71% affirmed that God still speaks through dreams, visions, angelic visitations, as was in the Old Testament, this is a big gateway for accelerating false doctrine.

The researcher reviewed the statements of faith of the following Pentecostal churches from their websites: the Pentecostal Assemblies of God-USA and the PAG-Canada; Watoto Church Kampala-Uganda; Full Gospel Church of Uganda; and Healing Springs Church of Uganda and found out that their statements of faith affirm that scriptures are final God's communication to mankind. However, much as they affirm that scriptures are the final supreme authority in all matters of faith and church practice, however, in practice, these statements of faith are not adhered to at all. They start entertaining extra-biblical revelations off Bible map, hence causing chaos. This fuels false doctrine. It is important to note that Pentecostal Churches have their heritage from PAG-USA AND PAG-CANADA.

Whereas the full Gospel Church statement of faith above emphasizes inerrancy and infallibility of the Bible, and its supreme authority, a good number of church members amounted to 74.42% need more than the Bible as final authority, hence believe in extra-biblical revelations.

C. Conclusions.

The study found that the major reasons why there were so many false prophets in church today, particularly Pentecostal churches, is because there exists the ability to discern. The Bible is so clear on how to recognize false prophets, but this is ignored and instead rely on extra-biblical sources.

This makes Christians get hungry for personal revelations, which exposes them to revering wolves in sheep's clothing. Extra-biblical revelations therefore, elevate subjective experience on the same, if not over, as Scripture. This not only undermines the authority of the Bible but also its uniqueness. Therefore, it is recommended that churches should stick to the authority of scripture alone to avoid getting astray.

Furthermore, Pastors should lead churches to embrace reformational instincts. A ruthless commitment to putting every doctrine, practice, and priority under the microscope of scripture.

D. Recommendations.

Based on the findings and conclusions above, the following recommendations can be derived:

- The churches should be able to identify misinterpretation and application errors by coming up with position papers as PAG USA AND PAG-CANADA do on controversial topics.
- Churches should assess the damage the wealth and health gospel has affected the faith of contemporary Christianity.
- To create an emphasis of identifying wolves in sheep's clothing and their false teaching by putting in place an oversight and accountability mechanism to towards doctrinal purity.
- Churches should adhere to their stated basis of faith of scripture sufficiency and no need of entertaining extra-biblical revelation knowledge which is a fertile ground of wolves in sheep's clothing.

Theoretically the study identified poor interpretation of scriptures which leads to false doctrine in Churches. The study identified and recommend the need for Pentecostal churches to adhere to theology position papers on sensitive subjects from their parent denominations like PAG-USA AND PAG-Canada as their Pentecostal heritage.

These days' churches can become easily divided doctrinally because of co-ntroversy over theological positions or ethical stances. This was worsened by Pentecostal churches break away from PAG supervision and became independent, each one in its own quarter (Isa: 56:11). When it comes to tackling these issues, the church's statement of faith should mirror the position papers on these controversial issues.

Most statements of faith focus on the doctrines your church believes, but it doesn't answer other questions that come up in today's environment on new theological topics that might be controversial, hence the need for position papers from oversight bodies as the apostles did in Acts 15:22-30.

A position paper is a deeper dive into the practical aspects of some element of modern Christian theology. It does not replace a statement of faith; it applies your church's statement of faith to a particular topic for guidance.

Three reasons why position papers are necessary:

- Provides clarity for visitors – Position papers should be written in a way to be welcoming to visitors. They aren't just a list of the church's doctrines, but instead explain why your church has the views it has. By posting them online, you help visitors to know up front your church's positions on potentially controversial topics like the meaning of marriage, generation curses, NAR teachings on spiritual warfare, etc.
- A position paper shows church members what it looks like when the pastors and leaders of the church are wrestling through difficult issues, bringing biblical wisdom to bear on sensitive subjects. It gives a comprehensive resource designed to equip motivated believers with information to help defend and explain their faith. Examining nearly every key issue, person, and concept related to Christian apologetics, clearly explains various philosophical systems and concepts, examines contemporary issues and challenges, and offers classic apologetic arguments, all with the aim of giving readers the background to intelligently and persuasively talk about and defend their Christian faith with skeptics. Defend their Christian faith with skeptics.
- Provides unity for the congregation – Position papers help you raise and identify issues where you may not be on the same page with a potential church member. This helps you avoid a situation where you hire someone and then face unintended consequences and potential division down the road.

Position papers aren't intended to lay out every possible response to any scenario that arises. They are a way for a church – on moral and controversial theological issues – to bring their theological framework to bear on different subjects, and then speak into how the church addresses these challenges. By being clear, a position paper can aid the church's pursuit of unity of faith (Ephesians 4:3-6) among the congregation in all churches.

E. New Knowledge Created

This study created knowledge of the Bible interpretation which is at the core of every classical Christian school's curriculum. In fact, the Bible often stands alone as its own subject. Since the Bible is the only sure way God communicates with us, its of primary importance for churches to undergo these principles of Bible interpretation.

Bible Students should learn the skills of observation and literary analysis, so that they can become complete at Bible interpretation

F. Area for Further Studies

Findings of this study showed a significant effect of misinterpretation of scriptures causing false doctrine coupled with lack of doctrinal unity in Pentecostal churches of Uganda.

The study on the effects non-denominational independence of churches which deemphasizes accountability to any parent denomination, was also recommended. The study, further recommended that a comparative study may be done on churches to ascertain whether the leadership styles, the educational levels of leaders, the communication style of leaders and the leaders' behaviors have direct influence on the performance of Churches. Lastly it was further recommended that a study to harmonize all statements of faiths with church doctrinal practice in Pentecostal churches should be undertaken.

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